

Mobile Technologies applied to protect victims of a crime within the EU Area of Justice: RightsApp for e-Justice

D5.3 Journal paper

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document lists the journal papers resulting from the RightsApp project. In addition to the dissemination activities already carried out, the RightsApp research team has included in this document the papers in which the research team is currently working on as a contribution from the project's outcomes and results.

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1 JOURNALS

Although the COVID-19 pandemic has caused the postponement or even cancellation of the most part of face-to-face meetings (for instance, see RightsApp Deliverable D5.2 – “Conference papers”), scholar journals have continued their work. The RightsApp research team has sent two different contributions, one in English and the second one in Spanish.

1.1 Law in Context

The first contribution was sent to *Law in Context. A Socio-legal Journal*¹ (ISSN: 1839-4183) is an Open-Access journal that is a leading Australian journal in the Law and Society field. The Journal has published important scholarly works exploring the context and operation of law in Australia and internationally since 1983. It publishes socio-legal articles that explore the social, historical, economic, political and technological aspects of the operation of law. Figure 1 depicts the home page of the “Law in Context for the Digital Age” home page.

Figure 1: Law in Context for the Digital Age. Home page available at: <https://journals.latrobe.edu.au/index.php/law-in-context/index>

The contribution accepted for publication in *Law in Context for the Digital Age* is named as “RightsApp: Empowering Crime Victims through Mobile Technologies”. It addresses the motivation, background and introduces the RightsApp mobile applications and has been accepted in the *Research Notes* section of the journal.

1.2 Journal of Victimology

The second contribution has been sent to the *Journal of Victimology* (ISSN: 2385-779X), which is an Open-Access journal hosted by Open Journal Systems (see Figure 2). The *Journal of Victimology* is an international electronic journal published biannually. The aim of this journal is to publish research articles and review articles in areas of victimology, following a peer-review system. Its scope covers various dimensions of victimology research as victimization and devictimization, psychological care to victims,

¹ Law in Context for the Digital Age home page available at: <https://journals.latrobe.edu.au/index.php/law-in-context/index>

victims' rights, specialized support systems for victims, the victim in the criminal justice system and restitution justice, with a transdisciplinary approach. Figure 3 depicts the “Journal of Victimology” home page.

Figure 2: Open Journal Systems. Home page available at: <https://pkp.sfu.ca/ojs/>

Figure 3: Journal of Victimology. Home page available at: <http://www.huygens.es/journals/index.php/revista-de-victimologia>

The contribution sent to the *Journal of Victimology* is named as “RightsApp, la técnica al servicio de las víctimas del delito. un App pude brindar información sobre derechos y dónde ejercerlos” This is a contribution written in Spanish that addresses the RightsApp project background and results from a victimology perspective. It also addresses the use of mobile technologies to support crime victims.

1.3 Upcoming journals

In addition to these two contributions, the RightsApp research team has elaborated an agenda regarding journal publications beyond the funding period of the project. At the time of writing this document, the *European Journal of Criminology* is in the roadmap. Figure 4 depicts the home page of this journal from the SAGE editorial that offers the possibility to publish in open access. Furthermore, it has a 5-Year Impact Factor of 2.037. However, the journal turnaround is very long.

Figure 4: “European Journal of Criminology” home page

The immediate steps that we decided to follow are:

1. Sending a contribution to the next *AI Approaches to the Complexity of Legal Systems (AICOL)*. AICOL is a well-known and stable Scientific Workshop with a long research track at LNAI (<https://www.springer.com/gp/book/9783030001773>). The next issue will be published in February 2021, and AICOL will be held at the *33rd International Conference on Legal Knowledge and Information Systems (JURIX-2020)* (<https://jurix2020.law.muni.cz/>). To respect the OA conditions, the paper will be uploaded at SSRN and Zenodo just after December 9th, the date in which AICOL will take place, after the double-bind peer-review process.
2. Writing a chapter for the Springer volume: P. Casanovas, J.J. Moreso, *Anchoring Institutions. Democracy and Regulations in a Global and Semi-automated World*. Chapter: “RightsAPP: enhancing victims’ rights in the European Union”. This volume will be published at *Springer Law, Governance and Technology Series*, early in 2021. To respect the Open Access conditions, the chapter will be stored at UAB repository, and uploaded to SSRN and Zenodo.